

*A non-profit environmental
research institute affiliated
with the University of Bergen*

*Edvard Griegsv. 3a,
N-5059 Bergen,
Norway*

Nansen Report No. 185

A Case Study for the Ocean CO₂ Injection Experiment on Hawaii

Guttorm Alendal
Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center
guttorm.alendal@nrsc.no

May 1, 2000

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1 Introduction

This work has been financially supported by a Subcontract from the Pacific International Center for High Technology Research (PICHTR), Hawaii, through a Re-entrustment Agreement with the Research Institute of Innovative Technology for the Earth (RITE) in Japan. It has been performed at the Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center in Norway.

The objective for this study has been to simulate the planned large scale CO₂ injection experiment off Hawaii in year 2001. A previous study [Alendal et al., 1998] injected the CO₂ at 700 meters depth which is shallower than planned for the experiment. In addition the background pH-value where too high in this previous study.

Tank experiments and the in situ experiments by Brewer et al. [1999] has shown that creation of hydrate is to be expected at the droplet interface. This will have influence on the mass transfer rate from the droplets, hence the droplets will dissolve slower leading to possible increased rising distance. There are presently no adequate parameterizations available but an ad-hoc parameterization has been used, the mass transfer is reduced with a factor 2. This will only be a zeroth order approximation and further studies are required in order to obtain a good parameterization.

The model used is the same as was used in Alendal et al. [1998]. It treats the two phases, sea water and CO₂ droplets, with an Eulerian approach on a staggered grid. In addition to momentum and continuity equations there are transport equations for temperature, salinity, carbon, and droplet density. The two phases interact through drag and mass transfer at the droplet sea water interfaces and CO₂ droplets are injected in a single computational cell through source terms. The model is fully described in Alendal et al. [1998].

2 Numerical experiments

Three different numerical studies has been performed. A base case which is similar to the base case in the previous study Alendal et al. [1998]. In the second experiment the mass transfer rate has been halved, simulating creation of hydrate at the droplet sea water interface. This is an ad-hoc parameterization and can only be viewed as a zeroth order approximation. The last experiment is similar to the first one but with a shutdown of the release after 20 minutes. The objective is to simulate 'return to background'. The different scenarios are denoted Base, Hydrate and Shutdown, respectively. Key parameters are shown in Tab. 1. The main difference between these numerical experiments and the previous simulations in Alendal et al. [1998] is that the injection depth is 790 meter located 10 meters above the sea floor at 800 meters. In the previous simulations the injection was at 700 meter 50 meters above the sea floor. The background carbon concentration has also been adjusted to a resulting pH-value of 7.5.

	Base	Hydrate	Shutdown
Grid dimension	100 x 15 x 70	75 x 15 x 100	100 x 15 x 60
Domain (m)	200 x 30 x 140	150 x 30 x 200	200 x 30 x 120
Bottom boundary (m)	800	800	800
Injection depth (m)	790	790	790
Injection x-coordinate (m)	20	20	20
Injection rate (kg/s)	1	1	1
Injection shutdown (min.)	NA	NA	20
Mass transfer reduction	1	0.5	1
Write datafile (sec.)	60	60	60

Table 1. Key parameters for the three different scenarios.

3 Results

3.1 Base case

The droplet rises and gradually dissolve the CO_2 to entrained sea water. After 15 minutes the droplet plume has risen approximately 60 meters and the droplet plume becomes 'steady state'. Figs. 1-2 shows droplet number density (m^{-3}). Since the slip velocity for small droplets ($< 0.5\text{mm}$) is set to zero, small droplets accumulate in the upper part of the plume. These small droplets will then be transported downstream by the background current. Droplet radius is shown in Figs. 3-4. The steady state plume continues to feed CO_2 to the sea water which will transport it downstream. The CO_2 enriched sea water experience reduced pH, shown in Figs. 5-6, and increased density. The CO_2 enriched water is therefore not only transported downstream by the background current but also downwards. Also notice that the pH reduction is smaller at the upper part of the plume, most of the CO_2 seems to be dissolved within the first 30-35 meters. The lowest pH is ~ 5.8 . in the base case.

Figure 1. **Base case:** Droplet number density (m^{-3})

Figure 2. Base case: Droplet number density (m^{-3})

Figure 3. Base case: Droplet equivalent radius (mm)

Figure 4. Base case: Droplet equivalent radius (mm)

Figure 5. Base case: Time evolution of the pH field

Figure 6. Base case: Time evolution of the pH field

3.2 Hydrate

The hydrate simulation is similar to the Base case but with the mass transfer reduced by a factor two. Since the droplet dissolves slower it is expected that they will rise farther before being totally dissolved. Figs. 7–9, showing the droplet density (m^{-3}), shows that the plume reaches steady state after 25 minutes, compared with the base case 15 minutes, when the plume has risen approximately 130 meters. The droplet radius is also decreased slower, as can be seen in Figs. 10–12. The slow dissolution makes more water masses influenced by enriched CO_2 . The pH fields shown in Figs. 13–15 shows that the layer with reduced pH water is thicker, compared with the base case, but the minimum pH value is higher. The lowest pH is ~ 6.1 which is 0.3 pH units higher than in the base case.

Figure 7. Hydrate case: Droplet number density (m^{-3})

Figure 8. Hydrate case: Droplet number density (m^{-3}) cont.

Figure 9. Hydrate case: Droplet number density (m^{-3}) cont.

Figure 10. Hydrate Case: Droplet equivalent radius (mm)

Figure 11. Hydrate Case: Droplet equivalent radius (mm) cont.

Figure 12. Hydrate Case: Droplet equivalent radius (mm) cont.

Figure 13. Hydrate case: Time evolution of the pH field

Figure 14. Hydrate case: Time evolution of the pH field

Figure 15. Hydrate case: Time evolution of the pH field cont.

3.3 Shutdown

This case is similar to the Base but with a shutdown of the CO₂ source after 20 minutes. Fig. 16 shows time evolution of the pH field after the shutdown. It shows a layer, ~ 60 meters thick, of water with reduced pH transported downstream by the background current. The model domain in the along stream direction is too small to see any diffusion of the pH field. The model domain could be extended further downstream but a CPU cheaper way would be to feed the result into diffusion model.

Figure 16. Time evolution of the pH field after shutdown of the CO₂ source.

4 Conclusions

Three different simulations of the Hawaii experiment have been performed. The base case show the same features as in the previous study by Alendal et al. [1998]. Not unexpected the reduced mass transfer caused by hydrate formation will expose larger water masses to the injected CO₂ giving less pH reduction. This may reduce possible biological impacts but may inhibit generation of a downward plume created by the density increase. The mass transfer parameterization used here is only an ad-hoc attempt to simulate effects of hydrate formation. If the mass transfer is reduced even further the droplets may reach the phase change pressure with a rapid surfacing as a result. Future laboratory and in situ experiments including the main experiment on Hawaii will give data to improve the mass transfer parameterization.

The code has shown to be to CPU and memory demanding for dissolution studies of the CO₂ concentration field. To be able to go to the next scale from kilometer to regional scale a simple advection/diffusion model will be better suited. Results from the present model can be useful as input to such a simulation.

References

- G. Alendal, H. Drange, and F. Thorkildsen. Twophase modelling of CO₂ droplet plumes. Technical Report 153, Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center, Bergen, Norway, 1998.
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